

Statement on the European Research Area Act January 2026

The European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc) welcomes the upcoming European Research Area (ERA) Act. Although the ERA Act has improved Europe's competitiveness, its impact remains uneven. Strengthening the ERA requires reducing disparities and placing researchers, and in particular early career researchers, at the centre of policy action. The ERA Act represents a fundamental opportunity to pursue a deeper fulfilment of long-standing and core EU policy objectives, including the original commitment of the Lisbon Strategy¹ for the EU

"to become the most competitive and dynamic knowledge-based economy in the world, capable of sustainable economic growth with more and better jobs and greater social cohesion."

Further, the ERA Act offers an unprecedented opportunity to address persistent and emerging challenges in Research and Innovation (R&I), including the prevalence of poor employment conditions for researchers and the increasing precarity of research careers, which largely affects early career researchers. It also offers the means to secure appropriate funding levels necessary for a competitive R&I ecosystem and to realise the EU's Fifth Freedom: the *"freedom of exchanging ideas and experience"*², or in other words, the Freedom of Knowledge.

¹ European Council. (2000). Presidency Conclusions: Lisbon European Council – Employment, economic reform and social cohesion. Towards a Europe based on innovation and knowledge.

² EU Parliament (1989), Statement on the Broad Lines of the Commission Policy.

Investment targets

Adequate investment is a cornerstone condition for a long-term strategic policy. R&I is of particular importance as a long-term investment and has repeatedly been identified as both strategically essential and in urgent need of reinforcement as a central pillar of the EU's future competitiveness. The EU should aim to finally achieve the long-standing target of **investing 3% of GDP in R&I, with at least 1.25% of GDP from public spending**. While private investment is a fundamental complement, **civil public R&I spending remains central**. This is especially relevant for blue-sky research, low technology-readiness-level research, and research with significant societal or cultural relevance that is not directly linked to immediate economic outcomes.

The ERA Act is instrumental in establishing **binding, transparent, and public investment targets for Member States**. This should be achieved through the development of long-term national policy and budgetary roadmaps that enable a gradual transition towards adequate investment levels and provide robust monitoring and accountability mechanisms. The potential synergy between EU and Member States funding instruments should be strengthened. This would enhance the effectiveness rather than inducing competition between R&I funding systems. Examples are the establishment of smaller national funding programs directed towards major European funding, and the coupling of national research funding to the EU Seal of Excellence.

The establishment of long-term R&I budgets and roadmaps with ringfencing of key budget posts is essential to protect research capacity and long-term returns from political volatility and shifting priorities. This must include **enhanced budgetary support** for researcher-driven, bottom-up, excellence-based programmes such as the **Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) and the European Research Council (ERC)**, which are longly celebrated and widely recognized as flagship initiatives of EU R&I policy. Such support should be safeguarded by avoiding the explicit or implicit absorption of Framework Programme funding into broader competitiveness instruments. Moreover, it is essential that these programmes remain **independent from political steering** and continue to be driven exclusively by excellence. The framework programme already contains ample directional funding, with the Horizon evaluation analysis highlighting how the extraordinary success of these programmes are likely due to their non-directionality. This independence is key to their future effectiveness in driving talent development, mobility, interdisciplinarity, and global scientific excellence.

Alignment of policies

Research is characterised by large-scale initiatives and growing interconnections with all domains of society. Yet, funding and governance remain largely national, resulting in fragmentation across instruments, policies, and working conditions. This fragmentation constitutes a major barrier to the full realisation of the ERA, and, in extension, of the Fifth Freedom.

Policy alignment should include R&I policies, investments, and programmes across Member States, with particular **focus on framework conditions, governance, and interoperability**, rather than through the imposition of top-down agendas. These efforts should begin with inclusive representation structures that empower stakeholders and ensure a genuine co-creation approach.

A specific and urgent effort is required to address fragmentation that limits researcher mobility. The **frictionless circulation of knowledge and researchers is a core objective** of the ERA, but this idea remains far removed from the daily experience of many researchers, and particularly for third-country nationals. Inconsistent or poor national implementation of existing EU directives still incur significant administrative burdens related to visas and residence permits. These issues are made more severe by the compounding effects of poor employment conditions. Moreover, the bureaucratic burden is often exacerbated by the repeating requirement of obtaining formal recognition of academic degrees in each country. Therefore, removal of bureaucratic impediments to the movement of researchers needs to support **automatic recognition of academic qualification by implementing the Council of Europe's and UNESCO's Lisbon Convention more fully across the EU**.

Alignment must additionally be addressed at the geographical level by supporting equal opportunities across the Union and by reducing regional disparities. This includes **strengthening Widening participation** policies and dedicated instruments to counteract asymmetric talent flows.

Research framework improvements

Research careers remain characterised by **precarious employment conditions, often involving short-term contracts and inadequate, or entirely absent, access to social security**. This situation disproportionately affects early career researchers. In some Member States, doctoral candidates are still formally recognised solely as students, while in others the legal recognition of these researchers as workers is actively hindered by national legislation. These conditions impose significant and sometimes unbearable personal costs on individual researchers, despite the acknowledged strategic importance of investing in talent for the long-term societal and economic objectives of the EU.

This issue needs to be tackled while respecting the division of legislative competences between the EU and Member States, through a combination of complementary instruments.

1. **Minimum standards for research employment** should be set at EU level, recognising the atypical nature of research careers compared to more standard employment trajectories in other sectors. This includes mandating that **all research workers hold EU-juridical worker status**, including at R1 (doctoral candidates) and R2 (postdoctoral researchers) levels, with a clear placement in the R1–R4 career scheme. Minimum level of equal treatment compared to permanent staff needs to be provided, including in wages and access to social security. Minimum standards should be especially **mandatory for all EU-funded research positions**.

2. **Attractive standards for research employment** should be developed in template contract types that can be used as reference for national implementation to reduce fragmentation and promote upward convergence across Member States and enable necessary national reforms. These should include reference to **entry-level for R1 researchers wages benchmarked against already upper-secondary teacher wages**, which are already institutionally surveyed at European level. Such model contracts should also be used in the context of a **28th regime concept for researchers** as a parallel EU-wide legal framework.

Minimum standards should be **mandatory for all EU-funded research positions**, ensuring the responsible use of EU public funding. This principle should also be embedded within the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R), so that EU recognitions are awarded only to institutions that demonstrably uphold researchers' rights and working conditions.

To achieve an attractive and genuinely free-flowing ERA, improved employment conditions must be accompanied by the **removal of mobility barriers**, including administrative procedures related to visas, residence permits, and social security. In this context, the establishment of a truly EU-wide portable pension system is essential to remove financial disincentives to mobility, whether by supporting existing initiatives such as RESAVER or by incorporating such mechanisms into a potential 28th regime.

Sustainable research careers are also shaped by **research assessment and research practices**. Assessment systems should align with the principles of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) in recognising a diversity of research contributions and prioritising quality, openness, and interdisciplinarity. Knowledge valorisation should adopt an inclusive approach that recognises societal, policy, and cultural impacts alongside commercial outcomes. At the same time, **Open Science** must remain a central pillar of EU strategy to ensure the free flow of knowledge and the development of a robust knowledge society. Thus, the ERA Act should consolidate and reinforce existing commitments to it, including open access to publications supported by secondary publishing rights and sustainable publishing platforms, such as Open Research Europe.

Safeguarding values

The EU is founded on strong fundamental values that must be upheld and enforced within R&I policy. **Academic and research freedom are fundamental values** of democracy that must remain central to both the current and future ERA. They are essential to innovation, public trust in science, and the resilience of the EU's democratic foundations.

Academic and research freedom should be safeguarded through institutional autonomy and transparent governance within research-performing organisations. This requires safeguarding and ensuring that **researchers at all career stages are adequately represented** and able to participate meaningfully in academic governance structures at all levels. An **independent European ombudsperson for academic and research freedom** should be introduced.

Finally, in a context of increasing geopolitical pressure against diversity, equity, and inclusion policies, the ERA Act must reaffirm the **principle of equitable opportunities**. This includes promoting gender equality through **mandatory and enforceable Gender Equality Plans linked to access to EU funding**. Inclusiveness should be further strengthened by addressing structural barriers, including those related to caregiving responsibilities.

Authors

- Nicola Dengo, 0000-0003-2534-7265
- Aleksandra Joanna Lewandowska, 0000-0002-7762-2890
- Norbert Bencze, 0000-0001-7108-5329
- Pil Maria Saugmann, 0000-0002-3548-0134
- Karl Kilbo Edlund, 0000-0001-7586-4119
- Linnéa Carlsson, 0000-0002-7123-3173
- Magali Weissgerber, 0000-0002-2999-055X

Information

This statement was approved by the Board of Eurodoc and published on 23.01.2026.

For more information contact board@eurodoc.net

or visit the website <https://www.eurodoc.net>

This document is released under the Creative Commons license Attribution 4.0 International.

Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, is a grassroots federation of 28 national associations of early career researchers (ECRs) from 25 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established in 2002 and is based in Brussels. As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research, higher education, and innovation in Europe.

